

CONSTRUCTION OF ENERGY EFFICIENT HOUSES IN CENTRAL ASIA AND THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN.

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Annotation: This article covers the process of building passive and active houses with energy efficiency in the territory of Uzbekistan. Requirements Teach students to think and remember as a small group on a topic that has been or should be covered, to recall learned knowledge, and to summarize the ideas gathered.

Keywords: energy efficient, passive houses, active houses, building heating, energy efficient houses

Construction of energy-efficient buildings began after the global energy crisis. The world's first multi-storey energy-efficient building was built in 1972 in Manchester, United States.

Serious thinking about what an energy-efficient home should look like began at the end of the last century. Experts from Austria, Germany and Sweden were interested in saving electricity and heating costs. Their research has shown that the overall energy efficiency of a home is affected not only by the heating system, but also by the relative lighting of the building, which has never been considered before.

In the recent past, when gas heating was cheap, people hardly thought about heat-saving homes. That is, the builder can not only heat the house, but also heat the street. Today, the situation has changed dramatically due to the constant rise in energy prices around the world. Builders have begun to think about building heat-insulating homes that will result in higher levels of heat loss. Heat in the room can also be lost through cracks in the walls and windows.

The heat loss of a building is 30-35% through ventilation, 20-25% through windows, 15-25% through walls, 10-20% from the roof and 20-25% through foundations.

The main factor influencing the energy efficiency of buildings is the efficiency and service life of the applied heat sink, widely used.

There are two types of energy efficient buildings: passive and active. An energy efficient home or a passive home is one that consumes very little energy. Heating of passive houses should be carried out at the expense of heat and alternative energy sources from household appliances from the natural heat of its occupants. Hot water supply is provided through the installation of renewable energy, heat pumps or solar panels.

Passive, active and mixed or, in other words, integrated solar systems can be used to use solar energy to meet the heat needs of buildings.

In passive solar systems, the function of receiving and processing solar energy is performed by the building, its rooms and structures, heat distribution is carried out by convection.

In active solar systems, special engineering devices for receiving, processing, transporting, collecting and distributing solar energy are much higher than in passive systems.

Solar systems use elements of both passive and active solar systems, which increase the efficiency of solar energy use.

The greenhouse effect in rooms with a passive heating system is based on the effect of the accumulation of solar energy by the heavy structures of the building and the effects of the heat transfer convention. Most of the south-facing walls include glass buildings, simple greenhouses, buildings with gutters, and buildings with façade heating systems that provide heat efficiency. Current Energy Efficient Buildings The second type of active houses generates energy on their own using renewable sources. The basic parameters of an active house are similar to those of passive houses. Creating a comfortable microclimate. An active home is a home that is able to provide not only itself but also the hotel, bathroom, pool with energy and heat.

Active houses were built in Denmark for the first time in the world, and although they consume as little energy as a passive house, they are also funded in many countries because of their ability to generate more energy and transfer it to the central grid. can find. Therefore, such houses are a source of income, not a source of expenses.

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